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INTERPRETATION AND THE APPARENT
SAMENESS OF CHILDREN'S NOVELS

The critical theory of the past few decades has focussed on the similarities of different works of literature—on archetypes, on considerations of genre, on intertextuality; yet for most of us, the reason for criticism remains what it has always been. Like Samuel Johnson, like Matthew Arnold, like T.S. Eliot, we want to determine what makes the poems and novels we consider good different from the ones we consider mediocre; and we want to explore what makes the works we consider masterpieces special. In other words, we still want to know how works of literature are different from each other.

For that reason, we assume that good books are those that transcend genre or archetype, and that demand our close attention to their distinguishing qualities—those qualities that we can, as we say, “interpret.” Above all, we assume that the act of interpretation will reveal the sources of uniqueness, somewhere below the surface, in a central core of distinct meanings and patterns; and we assume that in being distinct, such a central core is the exact opposite of the archetypal or the generic. In other words, distinctive details on the surface are evidence of uniqueness at the core.

That causes a serious problem for critics of children's literature. Most children's books are “simple,” undetailed, and consequently, so similar to each other that their generic similarities and their evocations of archetypes are breathtakingly obvious. Such books have few qualities distinct enough to need interpreting, and attempts to interpret them as we interpret important adult books reveal surprisingly similar central cores of meanings and patterns—cores not much different from the generic or the archetypal.

Of course, most adult novels are more alike each other than different. But when we suspect that there's little difference between an adult novel's central core and its generic qualities or its archetypes, we happily identify it as formula fiction, and happily acknowledge that it requires no individual interpretation. Children's fiction thwarts would-be interpreters simply because so few children's novels move much beyond the formulaic or the stereotypical. Lois Kuznets has shown how respected children's novels by both Lois Lenski and Noel Streatfeild contain the underlying formulas of popular literature for adults that John G. Cawelti has outlined: “both seem to have produced only a layer of realism imposed upon a stereotypical structure, which in turn rested upon an archetypal base.”¹ Kuznets suggests

¹Lois R. Kuznets, “Family as Formula: Cawelti's Formulaic Theory and Streatfeild's ‘Shoe’ Books,” *ChLA Quarterly*, 9 (Winter 1984-85), 148. Kuznets refers to *Adventure, Mystery, and Romance* by John Cawelti (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 1976).

that these books and many other “good” children’s novels are “individualized formulaic narratives,” as distinguished not only from crude formula novels, but also from more complex children’s novels, which she sees as open to interpretation.

Yet even those more complex children’s novels seem to have more in common with works of popular fiction and with each other than do interpretable books for adults. A quick glance through any journal devoted to the criticism of children’s literature reveals how frequently interpretations of quite different sorts of excellent children’s books uncover the same or quite similar patterns and themes: not only is E.B. White’s *Charlotte’s Web* as much about acceptance of one’s lot as are R.L. Stevenson’s *Treasure Island* and Virginia Hamilton’s *Arilla Sun Down*, but it brings its characters to that acceptance by similar means.

This apparent sameness of even important children’s books demands one of two conclusions. We can accept the implications of the critical endeavour throughout history, and say that “good” children’s novels are not in fact good novels, because interpretation cannot show us how they are different from each other. Or we can accept what our instinct tells us—that some children’s novels stand out, and are, indeed, especially worthy of critical attention, even though interpretation tells us that they are much like other children’s novels. If we are wise enough to make the second choice, then we face another choice. We may conclude that the similarity of good children’s books to each other makes children’s fiction different from adult fiction—different enough that it requires its own interpretive approach. Or we may reach a quite different, and, to my mind, more sensible conclusion—that in fact, children’s fiction is less significantly a special sort of fiction than a serious challenge to conventional ideas about interpretation and distinctness, that traditional means of interpretation are *always* misleading, and that the central cores critics uncover in complex adults novels do not actually explain what is special about those novels either. Perhaps Susan Sontag was right when she suggested that interpretation as conventionally practised “violates” art.²

I began thinking of these matters as I listened to a talk by Eleanor Cameron about time fantasies, children’s novels in which children of the present come into contact with people from the past. Cameron is the author of two such books, and also of an earlier discussion of time fantasies in *The Green and Burning Tree*;³ her talk called “The Eternal Moment” was about

²Susan Sontag, *Against Interpretation* (Delta) (New York: Dell, 1966), p. 10.

³The two time fantasies by Cameron are *The Court of the Stone Children* (New York: Dutton, 1973) and *Beyond Silence* (New York: Dutton, 1980). All further references to these novels are to these Dutton editions. *The Green and Burning Tree: On the Writing and Enjoyment of Children’s Books* was published by Little Brown (Boston, 1969).

books that have been published since that earlier discussion appeared in 1969. Near the end of the talk, Cameron said, "You may have noted the number of instances when I have said of one or another of these fantasies that in some respect it is like another."⁴ I had, in fact, noted exactly that, and been intrigued by it.

All the books Cameron described have a reputation for excellence; and the ones I had read seemed to me to live up to that reputation. In fact, few of these books are widely popular with children, simply because they are good enough, that is, complex enough, to demand some literary sophistication of their readers. They are the sort of children's books that adult readers who like to interpret literature find most attractive. Yet they are indeed very much like each other, in a way that the novels for adults that we consider excellent rarely are; and an exploration of their similarities clearly reveals how children's fiction challenges conventional ideas about interpretation.

Good novels for adults often have clear relationships with earlier novels that may have impressed or otherwise influenced their authors; but, perhaps because of what Harold Bloom calls "the anxiety of influence,"⁵ these relationships tend to be ironic ones. Distinguished novelists pay homage to their sources by subverting or re-inventing them; they become distinguished by making themselves distinct from their forebears. It seems likely, then, that the unquestionably distinguished children's time fantasies of recent years similarly pay homage to earlier books about contact across time—especially since this kind of fantasy is relatively new. Or perhaps more exactly, the possibility that this kind of fantasy might be considered a kind, a genre, is relatively new; for many years, Alison Uttley's *A Traveller in Time* was merely a unique novel based on an unusual idea, and it's only in the light of later novels that we can look back and see it as the first of a series of similar books.⁶

In fact, a look at earlier time fantasies reveals how very much recent writers do pay homage to them. It also shows how these earlier writers paid homage to each other, how Lucy M. Boston was influenced by Alison Uttley and how Phillipa Pearce was influenced by both. But surprisingly, the relationships of books by these writers are hardly a matter of re-invention, and certainly not subversive; there is influence, but little anxiety about it. Considered as a series in the chronological order of their writing, these early

⁴Eleanor Cameron, "The Eternal Moment," *ChLA Quarterly*, 9 (Winter 1984-85), 164.

⁵The phrase is from the title of Bloom's book *The Anxiety of Influence* (New York: Oxford University Press, 1973).

⁶Alison Uttley, *A Traveller in Time* (London: Faber and Faber, 1939). All further references to this novel are to this edition.

time fantasies are like the same picture seen in increasingly sharper focus. Each repeats the situation of the one before it in a way that makes that situation more obviously meaningful, so that one can look backwards and interpret the older books in terms of the meanings of the newer ones.

In *A Traveller in Time*, first published in 1939, a child comes alone to an old house and has contact with people who once lived there; and the solitary child and the place that survives time's passage come to be common features of most later time fantasies. So does Uttley's focus on the continuity of the house as the heart of the novel's meaning. The passage of time means that everything must change, so that everything must die; but the continuance of the house and of old ways of doing things within it means that time's passage does not matter, for despite it, things do continue in the same way.

In Lucy M. Boston's *The Children of Green Knowe* (1954)⁷, similarly, the word "always" appears again and again in relation to a house and its inhabitants. The family faces "always come back" (p. 18). "There's always a boat called Linnet on the river" (p. 32). "Tolly felt as if he had lived here always instead of just one day" (p. 37). "There is always a St. Christopher by an old ford" (p. 49). "Everybody who works here is a son or nephew of someone who has always been here" (pp. 80-81). Yet throughout *The Children of Green Knowe*, there are signs of disruption: the youngest Boggis retains the family name only because his parents weren't married, Tolly's mother is dead, his father has remarried, his stepmother distorts his own old family name into "Toto." Greene Knowe represents custom and continuity just as Thackers did, but now those qualities stand more explicitly for the past as opposed to the present; they are receding into it, and the house stands less for the fact that things do continue than for the wish that they might.

While that seems to reverse what Uttley suggested, in fact it merely makes obvious an implication of time fantasy that Uttley did suggest: that if the past can still be entered by people in the present, then it is not yet over. That represents a triumph over death, over the destructiveness of transience, over the separation of people from each other, even over scientific knowledge based on what our senses tell us of reality. Almost all later time fantasists consider contact with the past a sort of wish-fulfillment, a transcendence of what actually is.

Because Tolly's contact with the past represents his getting what he wants and needs, but cannot find in the contemporary world outside Green Knowe, *The Children of Green Knowe* has a psychological dimension not explicitly explored in *A Traveller in Time*. Penelope came to Thackers to be cured of physical illness; Tolly's malady is loneliness and lack of love, caused by the disruptiveness of the passage of time, which has killed his mother, destroyed

⁷L.M. Boston, *The Children of Green Knowe* New York: Harcourt Brace, 1954). All further references to this novel are to this edition.

his home, and brought war and disruption. Both children are cured by their stay in an old house and their contact with the past; but the psychological cure is more explicitly symbolic than the physical one. It's not just fresh country air that makes Tolly better; it's his contact with enduring values directly antithetical to those aspects of the world outside Green Knowe that threaten to damage him.

Yet Penelope did gain psychological strength, even if Uttley never directly says so; in fact, *The Children of Green Knowe* reads like an interpretation of *A Traveller in Time*, different only in its more explicit statement of themes. There is a similar relationship between *Children of Green Knowe* and Phillippa Pearce's *Tom's Midnight Garden*.⁸

Both books are mostly about children playing. But Pearce makes the Victorian Hatty an equal partner in the modern Tom's play, quite unlike the mysterious presences of Jacobean children that flit around the edges of Tolly's consciousness; and she describes Tom and Hatty's play from some distance, so that it seems to have more thematic relevance to the novel as a whole than did the more mysteriously evoked playing of Tolly and the Jacobean children. The games Tom and Hatty play all involve freedom from the constrictions imposed on them by circumstances, by adults, by the very fact that they are children. Again and again, they use play to escape—Hatty to escape her hateful relatives in the past, Tom to escape his "cooped up" life in the present. They have secret places to escape to; they climb walls to see over the constricting boundaries of the garden; they free birds from the gooseberry nets; and Hatty wants to skate because "I feel as free as a bird—as I've never felt before" (p. 116).

Not surprisingly, the very fact that Tom and Hatty can play with each other means they have escaped the confines of reality that isolate them in different times. The young Hatty can have a *real* imaginary friend, the old Hatty who lives upstairs can dream of Tom in her past, and Tom can enter that older Hatty's dream and actually play with the younger Hatty, because they need to escape confines and because they get what they need. Looking back, we can see that both Penelope and Tolly also got what they needed, in contacts across time afforded them by activities that usually offer only imaginary experience; Penelope dreams her way into the past and Tolly plays his way there, even though neither Uttley nor Boston insists that that is the meaning of her book.

Pearce also balances the benefits of wish-fulfillment with a consideration of its dangers; she explores the negative as well as the positive implications of escape, of freedom, and of nostalgia for the past. While both Hatty and Tom view the garden as a place where they can escape from the constrictions

⁸Phillippa Pearce, *Tom's Midnight Garden* (London: Oxford University Press, 1958; 1970). All further references to this novel are to this edition.

of their actual circumstances, it contains danger for both—and paradoxically, not because it is free, but because it is confining. When Tom walks on the garden wall, he realizes that he “had known only the garden, and a very little beyond its limits; now, from his walltop, he saw what seemed to be the whole world” (p. 83). At first the garden “tempted” Tom (p. 15), and it tempts him into a solitary existence, a self-enclosure that ignores family responsibilities until almost the end. The presence of a man called Abel in this tempting place has biblical overtones. Abel thinks Tom is the snake in Hatty’s paradise, and in a sense, he is; by escaping into her play with Tom, Hatty can ignore real life. Hatty says that if she’s caught talking to him, “Aunt Grace will say it shows how unfit I am to go anywhere with other children, outside, in the village” (p. 54). Later, her cousin says, “Hatty is young for her age. . . . Perhaps it comes from her being by herself so much—playing alone—always in the garden. . . . She should see more of the world” (p. 95). As well as representing the way a child’s world of play and fantasy is a necessary escape from the constrictions of reality, Pearce’s garden also stands for the dangers of that escape—its distancing from other people, its preference for the security of the limited known, its refusal to face what must be faced “outside.” As Hatty’s aunt says, “she doesn’t want to grow up; she wants only her garden” (p. 96).

But one must grow up; and both Hatty and Tom learn to move beyond the garden, and in doing so, to accept the inevitability of time’s passage. The last part of this novel is not about the joy of being in the garden, but the necessity of getting out of it. Pearce makes the passage of time *within* the garden a key issue, so that Hatty grows beyond Tom and the garden is therefore no longer an attractive place for him. She balances nostalgia with a commitment to the present and the future; and in doing so she makes brilliant use of the main quality of time fantasy: that it is both fantasy and history, and for that reason can balance the desire for escape with the inevitability of what is.

In this way, too, she clarifies a theme only implied in both *A Traveller in Time* and *Children of Green Knowe*; for while neither Uttley nor Boston draw much attention to it, ugly things happened in the past as well as pleasant ones, in both those books: Mary Queen of Scots did not escape despite Penelope’s wish that she could forewarn her, Penelope falls in love with a man who died hundreds of years before she was born, the topiary of Noah has been cursed, the children Tolly plays with died long ago in a plague.

Interpretations of the traditional sort I’ve just attempted—explorations of central patterns and meanings—would almost inevitably reveal important differences in three apparently similar, complex adult books. My explorations of these three undeniably complex children’s books which share a basic story idea reveals that they have quite different plots and quite different tones

but that their central cores are astonishingly alike. In other words, my attempt at interpretation reveals the opposite of what it should have—it shows how the theoretically superficial details that make these novels seem quite different are actually underpinned by the same themes and attitudes. And while we might expect similar themes in books with such clear generic connections with each other, we could hardly expect similar attitudes toward these themes; but interpretation of these books does in fact reveal influence without anxiety.

Upon interpretation, more recent time fantasies seem even more alike. Once Philippa Pearce made explicit the themes and attitudes only implied in earlier time fantasies, writers seem surprisingly content to restate those themes and retain those attitudes. I chose four fairly recent books to explore because, while their similarities were obvious, they did seem to have important differences from each other: Eleanor Cameron's *The Court of the Stone Children* replaces the old house of the tradition with a museum, and in Nancy Bond's *A String in the Harp*,⁹ an entire district of Wales represents the past; and because Janet Lunn's *The Root Cellar*¹⁰ is set in North America and Ruth Park's *Playing Beatie Bow* in Australia,¹¹ the circumstances of life in these books in both the past and present are quite different from those found in the English country houses of earlier books. These should be significant differences, ones that provide these books with the uniqueness we expect of good literature. But the more I explored these books, the more I found they had in common with each other—while, paradoxically, the more I confirmed my original impression that each is an excellent novel, and excellent exactly because its surface details *do* sustain a subtle central core of meaning, just as we expect good novels to. The curious thing, again, is that such different surface details seem to sustain such similar central cores. Before I consider the implications of that similarity, I'd like to show just how similar they are.

All four novels involve a child with family difficulties. Just as Tom's brother is sick in *Tom's Midnight Garden*, Nina's father is sick in *Court of the Stone Children*. In *The Root Cellar*, Rose's grandmother has just died, in *A String in the Harp*, the children's mother has died, and Abigail's parents in *Playing Beatie Bow* compound a painful separation by thinking of ending it and thus changing the status quo again. In all cases, the passage of time

⁹Nancy Bond, *A String in the Harp* (New York: Atheneum, 1976). All further references to this novel are to this edition.

¹⁰Janet Lunn, *The Root Cellar* (Toronto: Lester & Orpen Denys, 1981). All further references to this novel are to this edition.

¹¹Ruth Park, *Playing Beatie Bow* (Harmondsworth, England: Kestrel, 1980). All further references to this novel are to this edition.

has meant that something has changed; and as a result, a child is conscious that things are not now as good as they once were. Almost all the children express the wish that things had not changed; all want back the security and the comfort they have lost. They want their own personal pasts back.

But as the novels begin, these children are all lonely. There are two reasons for the loneliness, one physical, the other psychological; both involve separations. The child feels that he or she does not belong in the physical place he now resides in; Nina prefers her old home in Silver Springs to San Francisco, where she must live in a place that is "not home, but where temporarily she had to come" (p. 25). Jen says that Wales "sure isn't like home" (p. 50), and her brother Peter resents the move from his old home in Amherst to Wales; forced to move to Canada, Rose longs for her old life in Paris and New York, and Abigail resents her current home because it was a gift from the father who broke up an earlier one in a "two-car garden suburb" (p. 6).

While Abigail can't help feeling proud that her father designed the building she now lives in, the others find their new home horrifying. For Nina, modern San Francisco is "ugly" and Rose "had never dreamed of any place uglier than this one" (p. 16). In the first pages of *String in the Harp*, words like "strange," "foreign," and "unfamiliar" occur again and again; the kitchen is "completely strange, totally unfamiliar" (p. 10), and "Jen couldn't help feeling foreign" (p. 53). In fact, and like Tom at the beginning of Pearce's novel, the children all feel exiled—deprived of the security and comforts of home, they hate where they now must live.

The exile is not just a physical fact. It symbolizes a movement away from the secure innocence of childhood, the development of greater consciousness of the world and its nasty habit of not always giving one what one wants. But since these novels have been written for children who are themselves likely to resent the world's refusal to be what we wish it to be, rather than for adults who have supposedly learned how to accept it, they all provide good reasons for their young protagonists' resentment. They all demand more sympathy for their main characters than they do impatience with their refusal to accept—and they all do so by making them feel psychological as well as physical exile.

Rose, deprived of parents in early childhood, has been orphaned again by the loss of her grandmother. While the other children still have at least one parent, the parents are involved in problems of their own. The father in *A String in the Harp* is too submerged in his own grief over his wife's death to cope with the children's grief, the parents in *Playing Beatie Bow* must sort out their own confusing relationship, Nina's parents must cope with his illness and their new poverty.

Consequently, these children all are right to feel isolated—exiled from affection. Rose "came to the conclusion when she was about eight that she

didn't belong in the world" (p. 3). Nina's friend in the past, Domi, says, "I'm a little odd. Are you?" (p. 40). She is, for her love of old things isolates her from other children. Abigail is an "outsider" who feels "a hundred years older and wiser than the love-mad rabble in her class" (p. 4). In *A String in the Harp*, the children's loneliness is less an aspect of character than it has been imposed on them by their move to a strange land; but there, Peter, who used to be surrounded by friends, has become a lonely solitary.

Isolation is so central to these books that it involves characters beyond the main one. Beatie Bow is as feisty and difficult as Abigail. Nina meets both the "odd" Domi in the past and the "insufferable oddity" Gil in the present (p. 94). Rose first hates and then learns to admire the "frightening strangeness" (p. 22) of her aunt's family. In *A String in the Harp*, the children befriend the "shy" Gwilym, a solitary birdwatcher whose mother "wants him to spend time with kids his own age" (p. 34).

Furthermore, these novels contain many actual exiles in addition to psychological ones. In *A String in the Harp*, Gwilym's mother comes from elsewhere: "He doesn't quite belong, and she doesn't belong at all. Oh, she fits in, but she doesn't belong" (p. 49); and Mrs Rhys says, "I shall be a foreigner here no matter how many years I have!" (p. 137). In the past meanwhile, Peter relives episodes in the life of the harpist Taliesen in which he is exiled first from his own home, then from various other countries he adopts as home. In *Court of the Stone Children*, Auguste and Mamzelle have come to San Francisco from France; in *Playing Beatie Bow*, Abigail's father came from Norway, and in the past, the Bows and Talliskers have come to New South Wales from Great Britain. The family Rose encounters at Hawthorn Bay is almost as new to the island as she is; in the past, Will's family came to Canada from the United States, just as Rose does: "I guess what matters is where you belong. Me, I ain't always sure. I was born here but Ma comes from across the lake in the States" (p. 57).

In all these books, in fact, the central issue the main characters face is the one implied by their real or imagined exile: where do I belong? The words "belong" and "belonging" occur often in *The Root Cellar*, less often in the others; but in all the books, all the children finally learn that they belong where they are—Nina in San Francisco, Rose at Hawthorn Bay, Abigail with her mother and father, for as she says, "I have to go home, I don't belong here" (p. 107). Home is where you are now, not a place in the past that you feel nostalgia for. Even the children in *A String in the Harp* decide to extend their stay in Wales. What Becky says in that book is true for all of the exiles in all of these novels: "We've started to belong" (p. 356).

They can say that for two reasons. First, the events of the novel have brought an end to their isolation. They have found others who share their eccentricity and alienation from the norm, and in doing so, have learned

their need for psychological belonging; Peter thinks how he has "learned that he was part of other people and they part of him and he was glad" (p. 365). All the children who have felt alienated from their parents learn to love them again; Rose, who never had parents, has found some good substitutes.

But in addition, the children have had some version of what they thought they wanted—a return to the past—and it has first intensified and then brought an end to their isolation. As it does for Tom in Pearce's novel, the intensification occurs because their fascination with the odd experiences they are having separates them from others; his sister notices that "Peter just seemed to be getting further away from them" (p. 180), and we are told of Rose that "She had been so engrossed in the strange events of her own life that she had missed everything going on in the Henry household" (p.84). But, just as Tom's friendship helps Hatty, all do something in the past that helps the people who live there; and like Tom, all are helped in some significant way by those people. In the midst of exile comes the end of isolation.

Nina finds the clue that restores the reputation of Domi's's father—and while doing so, learns a socially acceptable way of dealing with her "museum feeling," gains the respect of new friends, and gets a summer job; she even finds a new apartment for her family, so that she no longer feels as imprisoned as she once did. Peter restores Taliesen's harp key, and his possession of the key brings an end to his grief and forces him to make contact with the other members of his family. Rose helps Susan find Will in an army hospital in Georgetown, and learns from that experience to value her new family in the present. As the Stranger of the Prophecy, Abigail saves young Gibbie from a fire in the past; and both her exile from home and the Talliskers' closeness that she observes while exiled teach her to value her own family in the present again.

In all these books, then, a physical impossibility—the meeting of different people across the barrier of time—represents an emotional possibility—the meeting of different people across the barrier of self. In fact, that point is made by all the books in some specific way. In a variation of Tom's meeting with the now aged Hatty at the end of *Tom's Midnight Garden*, Abigail in *Beatie Bow* meets and loves a man who looks like the boy she loved in the past, and who is actually the great grandson of the child whose life she saved in the past. In *A String in the Harp*, the children's father explicitly says, "I suppose the thing to remember is that if we're together then none of us has to be alone. Pretty heavy stuff!" (p. 154) A little less obviously, Cameron and Lunn both have large groups of once-isolated people sit down to a meal together.

These children come into contact with the past by means of a place that exists similarly in both past and present: the rooms of Domi's house, the Welsh landscape, the root cellar, the streets of Sydney. But whereas earlier

books focussed on the continuing sameness of houses like Thackers and Green Knowe, the settings of these more recent books have more in common with the once magnificent house Phillippa Pearce describes that is now divided into small flats. The place is quite different in the present than it was in the past—and that difference is as essential to the meaning of these books as it is in *Tom's Midnight Garden*.

While *Beatie Bow* takes place in both past and present in Sydney, there is no continuity of anything but the land under the buildings. In fact, Abigail quickly confirms her conviction that the past as it was is totally unlike the present as it is; but it is not what she thought it would be. The present distorts the past, as seen both in the absorption of Beatie's name into a game, and in the uncomprehending nostalgia represented by Abigail's wearing of an Edwardian dress and by her mother's shop, Magpies, which is filled with Victorian objects that distort the real circumstances of Victorian life. That uncomprehending nostalgia is like Abigail's treatment of her own past; she sees her early life when her parents were together incorrectly, through rose-colored glasses, and must learn to view them more accurately.

In *A String in the Harp*, a similar point is made by the counterpointing of Wales as it once was and Wales as it is now. As Abigail first felt nostalgia for the past, Peter first sees Taliesen's world as a green paradise; later visions give him a more balanced picture, in which Taliesen's feelings of pain and exile compare rather than contrast with his own. Meanwhile, modern Wales turns out to be less bleak and sterile than the children had first imagined it, so that the present takes on the qualities of the past as well as the past taking on the qualities of the present. At the beginning of the book, the strangeness of Wales contrasts with the familiarity of home; later, strangeness and familiarity balance each other, as Jen hears Christmas carols, "many of them unfamiliar but telling a familiar story" (p. 103), and as Peter thinks, "He and his father and Gwilym would always be foreigners . . . it didn't matter as much as he had once thought" (p. 246); for every human being is a foreigner to every other human being, and all must meet across a gulf.

In *Root Cellar*, Rose first feels she belongs in the past because the Edenic freshness of the past as she first sees it so contrasts with the disruption of her present life; "it all seemed brighter and more interesting than any place she had ever seen" (p.47). But just as Peter must live through the desolation of Taliesen's life, Rose must live through the desolation of the American civil war; and a symbol of that desolation is the contrast of a tree-less Washington in the past with the "tree-lined streets" Rose remembers experiencing in modern Washington (p. 179). Like Peter and like Abigail, Rose's realization that the past was not just paradise causes her to realize that the present is not just hell, and allows her to conclude that she belongs in the place she first wished to escape from.

Nina too discovers that the idyllic beauty of Domi's house in the past did not prevent violence and pain, and that she can find a way of belonging in contemporary San Francisco despite its ugliness. But in *Court of the Stone Children*, a paradox common to all these novels becomes clear. These children all first yearn for the past because they think it better than the present, and then turn back to the present as they discover that life is equally pleasurable and painful in both; yet in turning back to the present, all acknowledge that the past *is* significantly different—that in fact, to remain there would be to be truly exiled. Cameron succinctly expresses that paradox by replacing the house found in older time fantasies with a museum.

A museum does not represent the past triumphing over time by continuing into the present, but rather, what the present makes of the past; the French Museum contains the rooms of Domi's house, but as she says herself, "this is a kind of strange, twisted dream of my home, the same and yet weirdly not the same" (p. 43). A house that remains the same in a changing world represents a potentially stultifying regard for something no longer alive—a turning away from the flux of time. But it is our consciousness of the flux of time that causes us to create museums, in which the past remains alive through contact with the present, so that both may affect each other. Thus Domi contacts Nina, not because she wants the present itself, but because she needs something the present has to offer the past—the distance of historical perspective. And for Nina, the museum does not represent the past itself so much as something that allows her to cope with the present; when she speaks of her "museum feeling" as "being freed of the moment" (p. 17), she does not mean nostalgic immersion in a different moment, but rather, a special sort of health-giving consciousness that signals a temporary escape from all moments—a sense that time is not real which signals the transcending of ordinary reality.

In fact, these novelists all insist that the past's value for us is in its being over—in its being different from the present—because they all want to focus on how past and present, foreign and familiar, may meet despite their differences; they are not permanently exiled from each other. So all the books begin with the horror of change and separation, and all find a way of seeing change and separation positively. The word "pattern" occurs throughout *A String in the Harp*; it signifies the order and unity created by the coming together of disparate things that are themselves disorderly and isolated—including past and present. A similar idea is expressed by the chaos and anarchy Abigail first perceives in both past and present; as the two come together, she discovers the order in both that she is first blind to. And in all these books, it is not the past that heals the present, but rather, contact between the different values of past and present that heals in both the past and present. Peter and Nina and Rose and Abigail help Taliesen and Domi and Will and the Bow family as much as they are helped into greater

knowledge and self-acceptance by them. For Rose and for Abigail, moreover, it is modern assertiveness that allows them to act, while those who belong in the past express what is for them a socially acceptable passivity; similarly, Domi needs modern techniques of detecting forgeries in painting, and the existence of Gwilym's contemporary motor-bike is essential in Peter's task of restoring Taliesen's key.

In all these novels, as in *Tom's Midnight Garden*, the doorway between past and present closes after the two-sided healing, the balancing of present and past values, occurs; Nina loses contact with Domi, Abigail's piece of lace disintegrates, the root cellar washes away, and Peter returns the key to its rightful place. That healing has indeed occurred is signalled in all cases by the main characters conceding that they no longer require the contact.

But before that happens, all of these novels deal with the question most obviously raised by the magical coming together of past and present: it isn't logical or rational, so how could it have happened? In these books, characters who distrust the inexplicable are condemned as dangerously narrow—imprisoned in what is familiar and secure; as Dr. Rhys says in *A String in the Harp*, "People do not like not understanding, do you see, because as long as we understand, we feel we have control" (p. 196).

And the idea of control is central in these books. They all grow from their main characters' feeling that they lack control—that circumstances have control over them; and they all allow these characters to regain control by means of an inexplicable entry into another time, an event beyond reason—an event that ought to signify the opposite of control because it lets in the irrational. All are frightened by that. As Tom and Hatty are both distraught about each other's assumption that the other is a ghost, Nina is frightened "right to the gut of your being" when Domi's hand goes through hers; she feels "fear, or more nearly terror, and yet just as deeply a very powerful attraction" (p. 69). Peter feels the same way about his experiences with the key: "He was drawn to the key even as it frightened him" (p.66); Jen, his sister, feels constantly frightened by it. Abigail's first response to entering the past is "both terror and desperation" (p. 32), and Rose's first response to seeing a room in the house as it once was is to make it tidy as it now is: "she felt that by making her own order there the room would be less likely to change itself into some other room" (p. 29). While all these children feel disorder in their lives in the present, they fear the massive disorder implied by their contact with the past; yet their eventual acceptance of the possibility that one can have contact with others over apparently insurmountable barriers is what heals them, for it tells them that it is possible to live happily without that control, by accepting what must be accepted and dealing with it. Paradoxically, acceptance of what is—the world one is stuck with and cannot control—comes from acceptance of what ought not to be possible: escape through movement across time. Once again, the greatest similarity of

these books is their use of cross-temporal experience to signify the transcendence of psychological barriers and acceptance of the inevitable passage of time.

After commenting on the similarities of time fantasies in "The Eternal Moment," Cameron goes on to say, "But it is never alone the core of plot that is of foremost importance, but always tone, characterization, theme, style, evocation of place, and private vision that determine the difference in quality between one fantasy and another. . . . In this way there is no end to originality, to the ability of private vision to give us something new and treasurable" (p. 164). And that ought to be true; when I first contemplated this essay, I planned to show how these novels are different despite their apparent similarities, and I fully expected that interpretation would show me "something new and treasurable" in each of them.

I discovered just the opposite. As I analysed them, these novels began to seem more and more alike, not more and more different from each other. They all balance the same sets of opposites: home and exile, escape and security, the familiar and the foreign, the strange and the comfortable, fear and acceptance, isolation and togetherness, the disorderly and the patterned. All reach similar conclusions about these things, and do so by similar means; and while their settings are different, these different places come to mean much the same thing to the characters. My acts of interpretation seemed only to deprive these novels of their personality, and make the "personal" visions at their core seem astonishingly alike.

But the word "vision" can have two different meanings: not only what one thinks life is all about, but also, how one sees it. Any two people will see the same thing differently enough to make their description of it different; as I showed earlier, different degrees of explicitness make the atmospheres of earlier time fantasies seem different from each other. And of course, there are differences of tone and style in these more recent books also, so that Eleanor Cameron's presentation by similar means of a similar vision is quite different from Philippa Pearce's or Nancy Bond's or Janet Lunn's or Ruth Park's.

In fact, the Victorian Sydney that Park evokes in *Playing Beatie Bow* is distinctly crude and horrifying, and Cameron's focus on clear bright colors, particularly gold and green, and on damp, ferny places, gives *Court of the Stone Children* a feel quite unlike Bond's travelogue-like descriptions of Wales or Lunn's stark, understated descriptions of the horrors of war. *A String in the Harp* and *The Root Cellar* are more problematic, for they both have that clear, straightforward, undetailed prose that we find in *Tom's Midnight Garden*, indeed in much children's fiction; yet there is still something distinct in the atmosphere each of these writers create. In fact, there is something distinct about the atmosphere of each of these books.

I could, I suppose, be content with simply realizing that; but I would like

to *understand* it. Unfortunately, I know no means of understanding it but exploring it by means of conventional interpretation—by trying to relate the details that create atmosphere to a central core of meanings; and doing that makes these differences of tone and atmosphere seem less striking than they first seem to be—just as the differences in earlier fantasies come to seem less striking than their shared attitudes. Indeed, the mere fact that they do share those patterns and attitudes implies an impeccably logical conclusion: the distinctness in the tone and style of these books really doesn't matter at all, as it would in a consideration of adult novels. It doesn't matter simply because exploration of the apparently unique surface details that create tone and atmosphere only reveals how they actually point, not to private visions, but to central cores so similar to each other that they transcend the personal. These books are, in fact, more noticeably similar to each other than they are different; they lack any significant uniqueness.

That is impeccably logical. But it cannot possibly be right. Any perceptive reader must acknowledge that differences in tone and style do in fact make these books significantly unlike each other, even if the differences are not ones that traditional interpretation can uncover. As I suggested of earlier time fantasies, these novels challenge our most basic conviction about both style and interpretation—that distinctive details are worth interpreting because they do point to a distinct personal vision.

Furthermore, it may well be their shared central core that makes these quite complex time fantasies quite recognizable as children's books, even though we usually expect children's books to be simple. And if that's true, then the problems interpretation of them creates may well apply to the interpretation of children's fiction as a whole.

As I worked my way through interpretations of these books, I began to realize how very much of what I was discovering can be found in numerous other children's books also. Children's literature frequently combines fantasy with history, escape with necessity, wish-fulfillment with acceptance of what is—perhaps because our desires to entertain children conflict with our desires to educate them. Our attempts to entertain make much children's literature wish-fulfillment, escape from what is into what one imagines one wants; but our attempts to teach children truth turn that around and make much children's literature an escape from what one imagines one wants into what actually is. Consequently, time fantasy as Pearce left it and current writers practice it, a combination of what one wants and what is, sums up some central concerns of children's fiction in a particularly concentrated form.

Those concerns are thematic matters, ideas about and attitudes toward what matters in life. If children's fiction is indeed significantly different from other kinds of fiction (and it obviously is), then the main distinguishing factor may turn out to be, not necessarily the simplicity of style that

children's fiction shares with all popular writing, not even the shared set of archetypal plots and characters that children's fiction shares with most fantasy; it may be a fascination with the same basic sets of opposite ideas, and a propensity for bringing them into balance, so that both can be included in a vision of what life is. Even books as complex as *A String in the Harp* or *Beatie Bow* may be identified as children's fiction because of their concentration on the same themes in much the same way; and so may many complex children's books that are not time fantasies: to name just a few, *Charlotte's Web*, *Treasure Island*, and *Arilla Sun Down*, all in some way combine what one wishes for with what one must accept, all deal with freedom and constriction, home and exile, escape and acceptance, and all create balances between these extremes.

Perhaps that's not surprising; those themes are central issues in our conceptions of childhood and of the process of maturing, and children's fiction is more than anything else fiction for children and about childhood. Furthermore, the lack of anxiety in the way children's writers accept influence and pay homage to their forebears may imply a conservatism that nicely explains their constant dwelling upon themes of acceptance. Nevertheless, the possibility that children's fiction may be defined by a specific group of thematic concerns and a specific way of treating them would certainly explain why interpretation of children's books so often seems pointless. Since interpretation as we usually practice it is designed to reveal a book's uniqueness by uncovering its central core of ideas and attitudes, it can do nothing but reveal an apparent lack of uniqueness in the many children's novels that share a central core. Because it can only show that a children's novel is indeed a children's novel, it cannot tell us what we still want to know, and what it does often seem to tell us of adult books: how unique books are unique.

Consequently, my discovery that traditional interpretation could not explain how these books are different from each other does not so much deny their value as literature as it challenges our usual assumptions about interpretation. If interpretation of these books does not give us any insight into what makes them unique, then perhaps the information that interpretation of more "complex" novels provides is equally misleading. Perhaps the apparently unique themes and patterns we find in those more complex novels do not adequately explain their uniqueness either; perhaps we must search for other means of interpretation.

We must certainly do so if we wish to understand excellence in children's fiction, for traditional interpretation of children's novels can do little more than uncover the expected and the obvious. Until we develop a new approach, we will not understand how a children's novel can in fact be unique even though its characters, its story, its "simple" language, and even its central core of patterns and ideas are not.